

Machine-learning augmented global analysis of urban emission trends, 2010-2022

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Abstract

Quantifying emission trends in urban systems globally is critical for guiding effective climate change mitigation solutions and informing major science assessments such as the reports by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Currently available gridded emission datasets and self-reported inventories, however, are limited for analysing urban emissions, as downscaled products carry a significant national emission signal by construction, while self-reported estimates are biased by under-reporting incentives. Here, we develop a machine learning approach trained on a high quality bottom-up 1x1km² VULCAN inventory (RMSE = 39%, R² = 0.91) and apply it to similar cities globally. Comparing our estimates to ODIAC, we show that, on current trajectories, only 0-5% of global cities are on track to reach net zero and only 0-6% reduce emissions faster than their country. In 63–83% of cities, emissions are rising in lockstep with national trends. This is driven largely by Asian urban areas, where 88–95% of cities are growing emissions alongside their nations — though at a slower rate. Correlational analyses of the predictions indicate that cooling degree days is the most robust structural factor of urban–national emission divergence, though its direction reverses across regions with hotter cities lagging national trends in the Americas but outperforming in Europe, while population size shows no consistent association. These results demonstrate the value of machine learning for augmenting emission estimates at the subnational scale and highlight a stark gap between urban climate ambitions and current trajectories.

Keywords: cities, CO2 emissions, emission trends, emissions drivers, mitigation options

Main

Urban areas are increasingly cast as protagonists of the low-carbon transition. Commitments to city-to-city networks have risen remarkably over the past decades [1]. The C40 network unites 97 urban areas representing 920 million people, ICLEI counts over 2,500 local governments among its members, and the polycentric governance literature argues that cities can surpass national ambition precisely because they are not constrained by the pace of international negotiations [2]. Yet the emission trajectories that would validate this narrative remain largely unmeasured at global scale.

Tracking urban emissions trends remains a challenge for at least three reasons. First, the quality of emission estimates at the subnational level is generally lower than at the national level. Globally available gridded datasets, such as ODIAC [3], rely on nighttime lights proxies and large point sources to spatially downscale national inventories. However, the nighttime light composites used for spatial disaggregation are held fixed through the entire 2010–2022 period [3]. As a result, city-level emission trajectories within a country are algebraically identical to the national trajectory scaled by a time-invariant spatial weight, containing no genuine subnational temporal signal. Despite proliferation of this data for urban analyses [4–7], the applicability for analysing urban emission trends is limited at best, due to low variance in temporal within-country urban emission dynamics. Second, validated high-resolution emission estimates are limited to a few countries — most notably the United States

via the VULCAN bottom-up inventory [8] — and a small number of individual cities [5, 9]. Third, cities face incentives to underreport to networks like ICLEI; in the United States, self-reported city emissions have been shown to be underestimated by around 18% relative to independently validated estimates [10]. While recent studies have made progress at extending from single cities to national and regional scales using machine learning [11, 12], comprehensive global analyses of urban emission trajectories that go beyond downscaled (see e.g. refs [7, 13, 14]) or self-reported emission datasets (see e.g. refs [11, 12]) remain largely absent.

To address these limitations, we develop a machine learning pipeline trained on one of the best-available high-resolution national bottom-up inventories from the US: VULCAN 4.0[8] scope 1 emissions (emanating from within urban areas boundaries). For globally consistent definition of urban areas, we use the Global Human Settlement Layer Urban Centres Database (GHSL-UCDB), which contains a wide set of variables to characterise urban centres that are useful to train the machine learning model predicting VULCAN emissions. Using nested cross-validation procedure for conservative model performance estimates and an ensemble machine learning model using XGBoost and LME, we predict scope 1 emissions for more than 4k urban areas globally which have a sufficiently similar covariate space compared to US cities. While this approach is not without limitations either, particularly because the training data is not a random sample of the urban areas we predict on, these estimates complement existing datasets, like ODIAC or EDGAR that downscale estimates from the national level with an extrapolation of bottom-up estimates from the US. Based on the predictions, we then analyse urban and national emission trends for cities that are sufficiently similar to the US sample.

Results

Overview of machine learning predictions and regional trends.

Figure 1 presents an overview of ML emission coverage, regional trajectories normalized to 2010 values, and the degree to which urban emission slopes are structured by national context. The ML model yields predictions for 5,120 urban areas across all inhabited regions, with coverage varying substantially by region (panels a–b) due to varying similarity with the training data from the US. Of all cities by region, North America achieves the highest share at 99.5% of urban areas covered, followed by Europe (95.3%) and Australasia (86.4%). South America reaches 59.6%. Africa and Asia, despite contributing the largest absolute numbers of urban areas, 495 and 2,479 respectively, show lower percentage coverage (27.6% and 40.3%), reflecting that many urban areas in these regions are substantively different to US cities (for details on the similarity computation, see Methods).

Regional emission trajectories of urban areas and nations over 2010–2022, normalised to 2010, reveal divergent paths (panel d). In Asia, the national mean rises steeply across the period, while the ML urban mean tracks a substantially shallower upward trajectory. Urban emissions are growing, but consistently more slowly than their national contexts. Notably, Asia is the region with the strongest emission growth and the highest number of urban areas in our sample as well as across the world (Fig 1b). Africa shows a similarly diverging pattern between a rising national mean and a more moderately growing urban trajectory. In Europe and North America, both urban and national trajectories decline over the period, with the national mean declining more steeply than the ML urban mean. Here, urban areas are lagging the pace of national decarbonisation. South America and Small Islands remain close to their 2010 baseline with high within-region variability. Australasia shows a flat urban trajectory against a gently rising national mean.

The intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC), the share of variance in urban emission slopes explained by the national slope, reveals a fundamental difference between the two datasets that has direct methodological implications (panel e). Under ODIAC, the ICC approaches 100% in every region, confirming that ODIAC-derived urban emission trends carry essentially no within-country subnational signal: all variation in emission slopes is between countries, not within them. This is consistent with ODIAC’s design as a nighttime-light disaggregation of national totals, in which the spatial downscaling from national emission totals based on night-time lights are largely time-invariant from 2010 onwards and therefore carry no genuine temporal subnational dynamics [3]. The ML model presents a qualitatively different picture. ML ICC values are substantially lower across all regions: Europe 34%, Asia 40%, South America 56%, North America 50%, Small Islands 25%, and Australasia 0%, the latter indicating that within-country variation in urban trajectories exceeds between-country variation. Africa, at 13%, shows the highest within-country heterogeneity of any

region. These markedly lower ICC values confirm that the ML model captures genuine subnational variation in emission trajectories that is entirely absent from ODIAC, and that the near-perfect urban–nation co-movement previously documented using gridded top-down products is in substantial part a methodological artefact rather than a true feature of urban emission dynamics. This underscores the value of our machine learning pipeline compared to global gridded emission datasets.

Fig. 1 – Overview of the machine learning predictions. Machine learning prediction coverage mapped across the world (in panel a), the number of urban areas (b), the percentage of urban areas (c), the Intra-class correlation coefficient (d) and the emission trends normalised by 2010 values across regions, where light green lines represent the predictions of individual cities, the blue line the national mean and the yellow bold-dotted line the urban mean (e-k).

Urban emissions grow slower in national contexts where emissions increase but decline more slowly when national emission fall.

Figure 2 plots projected 2050 emission ratios for urban areas against their respective national trajectories, where a ratio of 1 indicates flat emissions relative to 2010 and 0 indicates net zero showing where urban areas would stand if they follow current trajectories on with a linear trend. Across both datasets, the dominant pattern is clustering along the diagonal: city trajectories track those of their nations, with most observations concentrated in the upper right quadrant where both urban areas and nations project growing emissions by 2050. This co-movement is particularly pronounced in the ODIAC dataset ($n=10,138$ urban areas), where the correlation between city and national emission ratio between 2010 and 2050 is visually near-perfect with urban areas from the same countries sharing almost identical normalised trends, corroborating Fig. 1d. The ML model (5k urban areas within the Mahalanobis support region of statistically similar urban areas) shows a greater dispersion around the diagonal, reflecting a genuine subnational variation in emission trajectories that the model captures independently of national trends.

Urban areas below the diagonal, growing slower than their nation, substantially outnumber those above it in both datasets in our ML model, indicating that urban areas are more commonly attenuating national emission trends than amplifying them. Urban areas above the diagonal, indicating that urban emissions are growing faster than in the national context are more common in high income contexts, particularly in Europe, consistent with the regional patterns described above.

City vs national emission trajectories to 2050
 n = 10,138 cities (ODIAC) . 4,735 cities (ML within-support)
 em_ratio_2050 = projected 2050 emissions / 2010 reference . Window: 2010–2022

Fig. 2 – Urban vs national emission trajectories extrapolated to 2050. Each point represents one urban area, positioned according to its projected emission ratio in 2050 relative to its 2010 level (x-axis: national; y-axis: urban area), where a value of 1 indicates emissions unchanged from 2010, values below 1 indicate net reduction, and zero indicates net-zero emissions. Both axes show $em_ratio_{2050} = \hat{e}_{2050}/e_{2010}$, computed by extrapolating the OLS emission trend fitted over 2010–2022 to the year 2050. The diagonal line ($y = x$) separates urban areas whose emissions are declining faster than their national trend (below diagonal) from those growing faster (above diagonal). Dashed blue lines mark the net-zero threshold on each axis. Light green shading indicates the quadrant where both urban area and country are on a declining trajectory; light red shading indicates the quadrant where both are growing. Point size is proportional to cumulative emissions over 2023–2050 under the extrapolated linear trend, providing a measure of the total mitigation stake. Selected urban areas are labelled for reference. Upper panel: ML XGBoost predictions (within-support urban areas only); lower panel: ODIAC-based trajectories (all urban areas). The near-vertical clustering of ODIAC points along the diagonal reflects the time-invariant spatial disaggregation of that dataset, whereby city-level trajectories are algebraically proportional to the national total by construction (see Methods).

Points in the lower left quadrant, where both urban areas and nations approach reduce emission, are rare and limited primarily to a small number of European urban areas in the ML model, including Copenhagen, and Berlin. Our model indicates that, if Copenhagen follows current trajectories, its scope 1 emissions will be reduced by 30% by 2050 compared to 2010. Copenhagen is famous for having set ambitious net zero targets.

These results reinforce that the predominant relationship between urban areas and their national contexts is one of co-movement rather than divergence, and the urban areas that meaningfully outpace their nations on decarbonisation represent a small and geographically concentrated minority. The

rarity of points in the lower left quadrant, where both city and nation are approaching net zero, underscores that urban climate leadership, where it exists, is seldom sufficient to compensate for the absence of national progress.

On current trajectories, only 0-5% of urban centres globally reach net zero by 2050.

Across all three emission estimates and the 2010-2022 window, the vast majority of urban areas are not on track for net zero by 2050 (Fig. 3). Globally, only 0-5% of urban areas meet our net-zero on a linear extrapolation of current trends. Under ODIAC, which however, is mostly a reflection of the national trend due to downscaling of emissions based on night-time lights, 3% of urban areas reach net zero under current trajectories. The dominant trajectory class across all datasets and all regions is growing emissions, with declining-but-not-on-track urban areas representing an intermediate group that is consistently larger than the on-track population.

Fig. 3 – Share of urban areas on track for net zero by 2050, by dataset, city type, and region. Stacked bars show the proportion of urban areas in three trajectory classes: on track for net zero by 2050 (dark blue), declining but not on track (light blue), and growing (red). For each facet, three bars are shown left to right: ODIAC all urban areas, ODIAC within-support urban areas, and ML XGBoost within-support urban areas. Net-zero status is determined by extrapolating the OLS emission trend fitted over 2010–2022 to 2050: an urban area is classified as on track if the extrapolated 2050 emission level is at or below zero relative to the 2010 baseline (i.e. $100 + \hat{s} \times 40 \leq 0$, where \hat{s} is the normalised annual slope in %/yr). Upper row: global aggregate and breakdown by city typology and four types [15]. Lower row: breakdown by world region. Percentage labels are shown for bars exceeding 5% of the total. The systematic divergence between ODIAC and ML bars, ODIAC showing near-zero on-track shares globally while ML shows a small but non-negligible fraction, reflects the absence of genuine subnational temporal signal in ODIAC disaggregation rather than a substantive difference in urban emission trajectories.

Dataset coverage and selection effects shape these estimates. ODIAC applied to all urban areas within our global sample yields the broadest picture, with 85% of urban areas growing, 12% declining, and 3% on track globally. Restricting ODIAC to the Mahalanobis support region (see methods), the subset of urban areas structurally comparable to those covered by the ML model shifts these proportions, with the on-track share rising to 5%, reflecting the higher concentration of higher-income, slower-growing urban areas within that support. The ML model applied within the same support yields decreases on track urban centres.

Regionally, Europe stands out as the only region with a substantial on-track population across all three datasets with 0-20% of urban areas meeting the net-zero threshold, consistent with Hsu et al [11], who analysed self-reported emissions in this region. South America shows a smaller but consistent on-track share, particularly visible in the ML and self-reported estimates. In contrast, Africa shows near-zero on-track representation across all datasets, with emissions almost universally growing. Asia and North America show predominantly growing trajectories, with declining urban areas present but on-track urban areas rare. Small Islands present a mixed picture, with high variability likely reflecting both genuine heterogeneity and small sample sizes.

The convergence across the ML model and between ODIAC lends robustness to the core finding: urban emission trajectories are overwhelmingly misaligned with net-zero pathways, and this is not an artefact of any single estimation approach.

ML indicates that 9% of urban areas are declining emissions while national emissions are growing.

Figure 4 decomposes the urban–national relationship into four trajectory quadrants, distinguishing whether urban areas and their national contexts are each growing or declining over 2010–2022. Globally, the dominant outcome across all three datasets is co-movement in growing emission contexts: 86% of urban areas under ODIAC (all urban areas) and 68% under the ML model fall into the quadrant where both urban and national emissions are growing, confirming that rising national trajectories are the primary driver of rising urban trajectories at global scale. The second most common outcome globally is urban outperformance within a growing national context, urban areas declining while their nations continue to grow, accounting for 10% of urban areas under ODIAC and 20% under the ML model. The quadrant capturing urban underperformance within a declining national context, urban areas growing while their nations decline, is rare globally but concentrated in specific income and regional groups, as described below.

Fig. 4 – City structural properties by net-zero trajectory status. Ridge distributions show the density of each covariate (2010–2022 mean) separately for growing, declining, and on-track-for-net-zero urban areas within each region. Vertical lines mark the median. Covariates shown are log population, log built area, industry and service GDP shares, mean heating and cooling degree days (HDD, CDD), GDP per capita, population growth rate, and built area growth rate. Only mL-predicted urban areas within Mahalanobis support region indicating sufficiently similarity to the training data are included.

The distribution across quadrants varies systematically by income type. Using the results from a global typology of urban areas [15], that groups urban areas globally into four types, the results indicate that among the lowest-income urban areas (Type 1), 97–98% fall into the both-growing quadrant across all three datasets, with essentially no urban areas on declining trajectories regardless of national context. This share declines monotonically with income: among Type 4 urban areas, the wealthiest group, the ML model shows only 33% in the both-growing quadrant, with 67% in the urban-growing/national-declining quadrant. This striking reversal in the highest-income group is the clearest signature of the asymmetric pattern: precisely where national decarbonisation is most advanced, urban areas are most commonly failing to keep pace, growing even as their nations decline. ODIAC, consistent with its structural dependence on national totals, shows a more muted version of this pattern.

Regional patterns reinforce this interpretation. In Africa and Asia, 88–95% of urban areas fall in the both-growing quadrant across all datasets, with no meaningful presence in declining-trajectory

quadrants. North America shows 100% both-growing under ODIAC, with the ML model revealing a more complex picture: 65% both growing and 35% urban growing within a declining national context, consistent with national grid decarbonisation outpacing urban Scope 1 reductions. Europe presents the most heterogeneous distribution: under the ML model, 43% of European urban areas are declining within a declining national context, genuine co-movement in decarbonisation, while 51% are declining within a growing national context, reflecting urban outperformance in countries yet to peak nationally. South America shows a similar pattern of predominantly growing trajectories with a meaningful minority of urban outperformers. Small Islands show the highest cross-dataset variability, likely reflecting small sample sizes and structural heterogeneity.

Taken together, these results present a more granular picture than aggregate net-zero statistics alone can convey. The global dominance of the both-growing quadrant confirms that urban emission growth is not primarily a story of urban areas diverging upward from their national contexts, but of urban areas being carried upward by the same forces driving national trajectories. Where urban outperformance exists, urban areas declining within growing national contexts, it is more prevalent in the ML estimates than in ODIAC, suggesting that genuine subnational decarbonisation signals are partially masked in top-down gridded products. And where urban underperformance is most concentrated, high-income Type 4 urban areas and North American and European contexts with declining national emissions, the pattern points to a structural lag of urban built environments behind national energy system transitions, a finding we examine in the discussion.

Urban areas in hotter climates systematically underperform their national emission trajectories

Having established that the majority of urban areas are not on track for net zero and that national context explains a large share of urban trajectory variance, we examine which structural characteristics are associated with urban areas outperforming or underperforming their national emission trajectory. We define divergence as $\delta = \dot{s}_{\text{urban}} - \dot{s}_{\text{nat}}$ (%/yr, both slopes normalised to 2010 emission levels), where negative values indicate that an urban area is decarbonising faster than its national context. Figure 5 shows Pearson correlations between seven structural covariates and this divergence measure across ML within-support urban areas, decomposed by region.

Mean cooling degree days (CDD) is the covariate with the largest and most consistently significant associations across regions, but the direction is not uniform. In South America ($r = 0.39$, $p < 0.05$) and North America ($r = 0.29$, $p < 0.05$), hotter urban areas systematically lag their national emission trajectories, consistent with the hypothesis that cooling demand constitutes a structural barrier to urban decarbonisation in contexts where energy systems are still expanding and cooling loads are growing [17]. In Europe, however, the relationship is reversed ($r = -0.48$, $p < 0.05$): hotter European urban areas outperform their national trends. This likely reflects the geography of European decarbonisation, colder northern European countries (Germany, Scandinavia, the United Kingdom) are driving national-level emission reductions through industrial transition and renewable deployment, while urban areas in warmer southern European countries (Spain, Italy, Greece) benefit less from these national trends and thus appear to lead relative to their own baselines. The sign reversal across regions underscores that CDD is not a universal predictor of urban climate leadership but rather a contextually dependent correlate whose interpretation requires knowledge of the national energy transition pathway.

Globally, log GDP per capita (PPP) shows a statistically significant positive association with divergence ($r = 0.13$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting wealthier urban areas tend to lag their national trends. Decomposition by region reveals this to be an artefact of between-region composition: within Europe and North America the association is near-zero, within South America it is negative ($r = -0.22$, $p < 0.05$) indicating wealthier urban areas outperform, and within Africa it is positive and among the strongest observed ($r = 0.35$, $p < 0.05$). The African GDP signal likely reflects between-country income heterogeneity within the region, urban areas in wealthier African countries such as South Africa and Morocco differ structurally from those in lower-income countries in ways that extend well beyond GDP alone, rather than a causal relationship between urban wealth and trajectory divergence. Taken together, these patterns call for a more careful interpretation of the association between urban wealth and climate leadership in prior work. Studies examining urban emission trends or mitigation ambition have consistently found that urban areas in high-income countries show slower emission growth or stronger target adoption [11, 18], but these studies compare urban areas across national contexts rather than against their own national baselines. Once national context is controlled for,

Structural correlates of urban emission trajectory divergence from national trends

Pearson r with 95% CI, similar cities only Divergence = urban slope – national slope (%/yr, normalised to 2010), Covariates globally z-scored

Fig. 5 – Structural correlates of urban emission trajectory divergence from national trends, by region. Horizontal bars show Pearson r between each structural covariate (panels) and the divergence of an urban area’s normalised emission slope from its national counterpart ($\delta = \dot{s}_{\text{urban}} - \dot{s}_{\text{nat}}$, %/yr, both slopes normalised to 2010 emission levels), for ML within-support urban areas decomposed by world region (y-axis). Error bars show 95% confidence intervals computed via Fisher z -transformation. Dark teal bars indicate statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$); light teal bars indicate non-significant associations. Bars extending to the right indicate that higher values of the covariate are associated with urban areas lagging their national emission trend (positive divergence); bars extending to the left indicate association with urban areas outperforming their national trend (negative divergence). All covariates are globally z-scored prior to analysis. As an illustrative example, the CDD panel shows that a South American urban area with above-average cooling demand ($r = 0.39^*$) tends to lag its national trajectory, whereas the same relationship reverses sign in Europe ($r = -0.48^*$), where hotter urban areas outperform their national trends — reflecting the geography of European decarbonisation rather than a universal cooling demand effect. Covariates shown are log population, log built area (km^2), industry and service GDP shares (PPP-adjusted), mean heating and cooling degree days (HDD, CDD), and log GDP per capita (PPP-adjusted), all averaged over 2010–2022. Australasia and Small Islands are included for completeness but should be interpreted with caution given small sample sizes and correspondingly wide confidence intervals. Data sectoral GDP was taken from ref [16], interpolating urban GDP values between 2010, 2015, and 2020, with the national trend, purchase power parity adjusted.

the wealth signal largely disappears within regions, suggesting it reflects national-level income and energy system differences rather than a structural property of wealthy urban areas themselves.

Log population shows no significant association with divergence in any region except Australasia, where sample sizes are small and confidence intervals are wide (Figure 5). This is notable given that urban size is one of the most commonly used predictors in the urban scaling and emissions literature [?]; our results suggest that whether a large urban area outperforms or underperforms its national trend is not systematically related to its size, once national context is accounted for.

Beyond CDD and GDP, the associations between structural covariates and trajectory divergence vary substantially across regions with few consistent patterns. In Europe, larger built area ($r = 0.17^*$), higher industry GDP share ($r = 0.10^*$), and higher service GDP share ($r = 0.09^*$) are all associated with urban areas lagging their national trends, consistent with the hypothesis that larger, more industrially diverse European urban areas benefit less from the structural post-industrial transition driving national decarbonisation. In Africa, moderate associations across built area, economic structure, and climate variables ($|r| = 0.18\text{--}0.35$, most $p < 0.05$) are observed, though their interpretation is complicated by the between-country income heterogeneity noted above. In Asia, statistically significant but practically negligible correlations ($|r| \leq 0.27$) across most covariates confirm that structural urban characteristics carry little information about trajectory divergence, consistent with the near-complete national dominance documented by the ICC analysis. The regional heterogeneity of these associations implies that no single structural urban typology predicts decarbonisation leadership globally, and that policy levers associated with urban outperformance in one regional context are unlikely to transfer directly to another. Rather, the dominant determinant of whether an urban area leads or lags its national trend appears to be the national energy transition pathway

itself, a conclusion that reinforces the primacy of national policy in driving urban emission trajectories documented throughout this analysis.

Discussion

We assessed urban emission trajectories across over 11k urban areas in 162 countries between 2010 and 2022 by triangulating two methodologically distinct ML-based emission estimates with spatially downscaled gridded data. Our ML model, trained on the VULCAN bottom-up inventory [19] and applied globally via Mahalanobis-distance matching, achieves [$R^2 = .91$, RMSE = 39%] on held-out geographic folds, demonstrating generalisation beyond the US training context. Across all three datasets, fewer than one in ten urban areas is on track to reach net zero by 2050, with the vast majority of urban areas tracking rising national trajectories. The relative performance of urban areas with respect to their national context is, however, asymmetric: in growing national contexts urban areas tend to grow more slowly than their nations, while in declining national contexts they tend to decline more slowly.

The near-total absence of urban areas on net-zero trajectories is consistent with, and substantially extends, prior evidence on the gap between stated urban climate ambition and measured outcomes. Studies based on self-reported inventories have been limited to urban areas participating in voluntary reporting networks, typically overrepresenting high-income, high-ambition urban areas [11, 20]. Our ML approach addresses this directly: by training on the independently validated VULCAN inventory rather than self-reported data, and by applying the model to structurally similar urban areas globally, we provide estimates that are not subject to the systematic underreporting bias documented by Gurney et al. [10], who found that US cities underreport emissions by approximately 18% on average relative to VULCAN. The concentration of on-track urban areas in Europe and, to a lesser extent, South America, and their near-total absence in Africa, Asia, and North America, points to deep structural inequalities in urban decarbonisation capacity. This is broadly consistent with evidence across 13,189 urban areas showing that high-income countries are the only region with consistent declining trends in fossil fuel CO₂ emissions, while regions experiencing rapid economic growth show sustained increases [14].

The asymmetric pattern of urban relative performance, outperformance in growing national contexts, underperformance in declining ones, has not, to our knowledge, been documented at global scale. The outperformance of urban areas in growing national contexts aligns with longstanding evidence on agglomeration efficiency: the concentration of population and economic activity in urban areas can reduce per-unit energy intensity relative to dispersed rural energy use, and the structural shift toward service-based economies tends to slow emission growth relative to national averages that still include expanding rural industrialisation [21]. The underperformance in declining national contexts is the more consequential finding. National emission reductions in high-income countries have been driven primarily by electricity grid decarbonisation, the rapid substitution of fossil fuels by renewables, and by deindustrialisation, mechanisms identified by Le Quere et al. as explaining declining emissions across 18 developed economies [22]. These are system-level transitions that largely bypass the direct jurisdiction of urban governments. Urban areas, by contrast, are embedded in built environments, transport systems, and industrial legacies whose transformation is constrained by well-documented carbon lock-in spanning infrastructural, institutional, and behavioural dimensions [23, 24]. When the national electricity grid decarbonises, territorial Scope 1 emissions within urban boundaries, from buildings, transport, and remaining industry, may decline more slowly than the national average, which disproportionately benefits from rapid grid transition. This interpretation is consistent with the governance literature documenting a persistent gap between national policy ambition and urban implementation capacity, particularly in building renovation, transport electrification, and land-use change [25, 26].

These findings carry important implications for climate governance. The narrative of urban areas as frontrunners of decarbonisation requires significant qualification: while urban areas moderate emission growth where national energy systems are still expanding, this advantage reverses where advanced national decarbonisation is underway, precisely the contexts where deepest absolute cuts are required to meet Paris Agreement targets. Achieving net zero in already-declining national contexts will require targeted support for the urban-scale transitions, building renovation, modal shift in transport, and localised industrial transformation, that grid decarbonisation alone cannot deliver [26, 27]. These transitions are slower, more institutionally complex, and more costly than grid-level

change, and they require a redistribution of both governance authority and financial resources toward urban governments that most national climate frameworks do not yet reflect.

Several limitations merit acknowledgement. The geographic coverage of our ML model is bounded by Mahalanobis-distance comparability to the US urban context in which VULCAN was developed, which underrepresents urban areas in Sub-Saharan Africa and parts of South and Southeast Asia, the regions where future urban emission growth will be most consequential. Our model implies that the relationship between urban predictors, like urban form, affluence, heating and cooling needs are also applicable in other areas of the world. This is, of course, a simplification of the real relationship meaning our results approximate the true emissions in these urban areas. Hence, like other data products, such as self-reported emissions [12] facing misreporting incentives and inconsistent measurement of emissions, or gridded data products like ODIAC[3] and EDGAR using spatial proxies to downscale emissions from the national level, our data also has its limitations but complements these products by using a high quality bottom-up inventory – an approach that, to our knowledge, no prior study has used. Future work should extend this analysis as longer and more geographically representative emission time series become available, extend the training data to potentially covering geographically more diverse urban areas, using atmospheric modelling outputs with space-based measurements of urban emissions as a model input where available (e.g. data from ref [9]).

Methods

To better quantify the emission uncertainty in cities across the globe, we develop a machine learning pipeline that predicts the gap between the widely available urban emission dataset ODIAC, which uses nighttime lights and large point sources to downscale national inventory-based estimates, and high-quality estimates available for the US and China.

Datasets

The Open-source Data Inventory for Anthropogenic CO₂ (ODIAC) [3] is a high-resolution global emissions dataset that estimates fossil fuel CO₂ emissions at a spatial resolution of 1 km, with annual coverage extending back to 2000. It combines national emissions statistics with satellite observations of night-time lights to spatially allocate emissions, offering detailed insights into urban and regional emission patterns. ODIAC’s fine spatial granularity and long temporal coverage have made it a key resource in the study of urban carbon footprints, enabling researchers to analyze emission trends, validate bottom-up inventories, and support policy assessments. Its transparent methodology and open access have significantly advanced the field of urban emission estimation. Despite its strengths, ODIAC’s reliance on night-time light data for spatial disaggregation can introduce uncertainties [28], particularly in regions with rapid urban growth or limited electrification, where light intensity may not accurately reflect emission sources [29, 30].

The VULCAN dataset [19, 31] provides high-resolution, bottom-up estimates of fossil fuel CO₂ emissions across the United States at sub-kilometer spatial scales and hourly temporal resolution for recent years. It integrates detailed local activity data, including transportation, industrial processes, residential and commercial fuel use, and power generation, combined with atmospheric and census information to spatially and temporally disaggregate emissions. VULCAN’s approach leverages extensive sector-specific data sources and emission factors, enabling precise characterization of urban and regional emission patterns. This fine-scale temporal and spatial detail supports atmospheric inversion studies and validation of remote sensing-based emission inventories. While VULCAN’s detailed coverage and methodological rigor provide a valuable complement to global datasets, its scope is currently limited to the U.S. [19].

Table 1 – Data sets and emission estimates used

Dataset	Spatial coverage	Resolution	Temporal coverage	Unit of measurement	data set version
ODIAC	global	0.01 × 0.01 (~ 1 × 1km ²)	2000-2022	tonne carbon/cell	v2023
VULCAN	U.S.	0.01 × 0.01 (~ 1 × 1km ²)	2010-2022	tonne carbon/cell	4.0

Data Preprocessing: emission data

We attribute emissions to cities, and we use the best available gridded emission datasets. We take the following steps.

First, harmonize the measurement units from all datasets. ODIAC and VULCAN report in tonne C/cell. Hence we use established approaches to transform the measurements [32] into tonne CO₂/cell and multiply by the molecular weight ratio $\frac{44}{12}$ to obtain tonne CO₂/cell. The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) provides surface flux data representing the exchange of atmospheric constituents (e.g., CO₂, CH₄) between the Earth’s surface and the atmosphere. These fluxes are reported in units of kilograms per square meter per second ($kgm^{-2}s^{-2}$), indicating the mass transferred through a unit area over time. The data are spatially resolved on a global grid, with each grid cell indexed by coordinates (i, j), and temporally organized by month (m). Therefore, we transform this to monthly emission estimates as follows:

$$E_{i,j,m} = \frac{\text{flux}_{i,j,m} \times A_{i,j} \times s_m}{1000},$$

where $A_{i,j}$ is the cell area on the Earth’s surface (in m²), s_m is the number of seconds in month m , and the factor 1/1000 converts kilograms to tonnes. Summing over $m = 1 \dots 12$ yields the annual emission tonne CO₂/cell.

Second, we carved out the emissions from each VULCAN and ODIAC grid to the urban boundaries defined in the GHS-UCDB 2024 [33]. We reprojected both raster and vector data to a Mollweide equal-area projection. Our equal-area reprojection ensured accurate area calculations and avoided high-latitude distortion. For each grid cell, we then determined if the cell lies entirely or partly inside a urban area polygon. If it lies fully inside the urban area, we retain its full emissions. If the cell intersects the boundary, we computed the intersection fraction $f_{i,j}$ and multiplied the cell’s emission by $f_{i,j}$. For each urban area, we summed all intersected cells to obtain total CO_2 emissions.

Data Preprocessing: machine learning predictors

Table 2 – Predictors used in the machine learning model

Dataset	Variable	Variable (official)	Time-range	Interpolation
GHSL	Total population count per grid cell	GH_POP_TOT_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Exponential
GHSL	GDP growth (sector or urban center)	SC_SEC_GDP_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Exponential
GHSL	Non-residential built-up surface per cap.	GH_BPC_NRE_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Residential built-up surface per cap.	GH_BPC_RES_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Total built-up surface per capita	GH_BPC_TOT_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Non-residential built-up area	GH_BUS_NRE_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Residential built-up area	GH_BUS_RES_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Total built-up area	GH_BUS_TOT_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Non-residential built-up volume	GH_BUV_NRE_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Residential built-up volume	GH_BUV_RES_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Total built-up volume	GH_BUV_TOT_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Built-up surface in urban core	GH_XST_S30_XXXX	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020	Linear
GHSL	Average building height	GH_BUH_AVG_XXXX	2020	NaN
GHSL	Std. dev. of building height	GH_BUH_STD_XXXX	2020	NaN
GHSL	Maximum building height	GH_BUH_MAX_XXXX	2020	NaN
GHSL	Average building height	HZ_CEV_HW_XXXX	2005, 2010, 2015	NaN
GHSL	Total road length in urban center	IN_ROA_LEN_XXXX	2024	NaN
GHSL	Road network density in urban center	IN_ROA_DEN_XXXX	2024	NaN
GHSL	Urban centre area (km ²)	GC_UCA_KM2_XXXX	2025	NaN

Dataset	Variable	Variable (official)	Time-range	Interpolation
Lizana et al[34]	Heating Degree Days	hdd	2024	NaN
Lizana et al[34]	Cooling Degree Days	cdd	2024	NaN
Oda et al[3]	ODIAC CO ₂ emissions	tCO ₂ eq	2000-2023, monthly aggregated to yearly	NaN

For our machine learning model, we extracted a range of predictor variables from the 2024 release of the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL)[33], including population size, economic growth, built-environment characteristics, road network metrics, heating and cooling degree days, and the urban sprawl index (see Table 3). Time-series predictors available at five-year intervals between 2000 and 2020 were interpolated to annual values using exponential or linear interpolation (see Section below); predictors available only for specific years were included directly.

For each predictor available at two discrete years t_0 and t_1 , we compute intermediate values $y(t)$ for $t_0 \leq t \leq t_1$ using one of two interpolation schemes.

We apply the following exponential (compound) interpolation to strictly positive, compound-growth variables. Given (t_0, y_0) and (t_1, y_1) ,

$$y(t) = y_0 \left(\frac{y_1}{y_0} \right)^{\frac{t-t_0}{t_1-t_0}}, \quad t_0 \leq t \leq t_1, \quad (1)$$

with constant annual compound growth rate

$$r_{\text{exp}} = \left(\frac{y_1}{y_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{t_1-t_0}} - 1. \quad (2)$$

The linear interpolation is applied to variables exhibiting approximately linear change. Given (t_0, y_0) and (t_1, y_1) ,

$$y(t) = y_0 + \frac{y_1 - y_0}{t_1 - t_0} (t - t_0), \quad t_0 \leq t \leq t_1, \quad (3)$$

with average annual growth rate

$$r_{\text{lin}} = \frac{y_1 - y_0}{(t_1 - t_0) y_0}. \quad (4)$$

After generating a balanced panel via interpolation, we merged each interpolated variable $y(t)$ with the corresponding annual emission observations for year t . For non-temporal predictors available in only a single year (e.g. static land-use classifications), we treated each urban area as having the same predictor value across all years. In other words, if a predictor is reported for urban area i in year t^* only, we assigned that value to urban area i for every $t \in [2000, 2020]$. For non-temporal predictors with observations in several isolated years but insufficient data for interpolation (e.g. infrastructure metrics surveyed at irregular intervals), we matched each urban area-year record to the nearest available observation year t_j , i.e. for a target year t we used the predictor value observed at

$$t_j = \arg \min_{t_k \in T_i} |t - t_k|,$$

where T_i is the set of survey years for urban area i . This approach ensured that every urban area-year sample in our modeling dataset had a complete set of predictors, either interpolated or directly assigned.

Machine learning setup: hyperparameters and predictors, and performance

We then applied an XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) model to predict urban emissions. Instead of fitting a single equation to the data, as in ordinary least squares regression, XGBoost builds a sequence of decision trees where each new tree focuses on the residual errors of the previous ones, progressively improving the ensemble’s predictions [35]. A decision tree works by asking a sequence of threshold questions, such as “Is total built-up area above a certain value?”, until it reaches a predicted emission level. We tuned eight hyperparameters: maximum tree depth, number of estimators, learning rate, subsample fraction, column subsample fraction, L1 regularisation, L2 regularisation, minimum child weight, and minimum split gain.

To prevent information leakage across years from the same urban area, we partitioned the data by city using a GroupKFold scheme. We implemented a nested cross-validation framework with three outer folds and three inner folds. In each inner fold, we used Optuna’s Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) sampler [36] with 40 trials to minimise a penalised objective.

where the penalty term discourages solutions that overfit the training split. Optimal hyperparameters from the inner loop were applied to train on the full outer training fold and evaluated on the held-out outer test fold. Consensus hyperparameters across folds were computed as the median across outer folds (geometric mean for the learning rate), and a final model was trained on the full dataset using these consensus values. Per-fold performance is reported in Table ??.

We additionally trained a Linear Mixed Effects (LME) model [?] as a time-aware ensemble member. The LME model includes city-level random intercepts and random slopes on ODIAC emissions, together with year fixed effects to capture global emission shocks. This design allows each city to have its own sensitivity between nighttime-light-based emissions and actual combustion. The LME model was trained on the same GroupKFold splits as XGBoost, ensuring a fair out-of-fold comparison. Per-fold performance is reported in Table 3.

Final predictions combine both models via a log-space blend:

$$\hat{z}_{\text{blend}} = (1 - w_{\text{LME}}) \hat{z}_{\text{XGB}} + w_{\text{LME}} \hat{z}_{\text{LME}}, \quad (5)$$

where \hat{z} denotes predictions in log space and w_{LME} is capped at 0.5 to ensure XGBoost always contributes at least equally. The optimal weight $w_{\text{LME}} = 0.30$ was selected by maximising blended OOF R^2 via grid search over $[0, 0.5]$.

The blend model achieved a mean absolute error of 27.9% in log space (equivalent to a median multiplicative factor of $e^{0.28} \approx 1.32$), with no systematic directional bias (aggregate OOF $\text{MPE}_{\log} = -0.80\%$). Blended performance is summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 – Blended model out-of-fold performance (log space). $w_{\text{LME}} = 0.30$, $w_{\text{LME}} = 0.30$. Performance denotes mean across the outer folds.

Model	R^2	RMSE	MPE_{\log}	MAPE_{\log}
XGBoost (OOF)	0.9061	0.3928	-0.37	28.54
LME (OOF)	0.8839	0.4368	-1.80	33.06
Blend $w_{\text{LME}} = 0.30$	0.9113	0.3819	-0.80	27.92

Mahalanobis-based identification of urban areas sufficiently similar to predict urban emissions

We found that the XGBoost model tuned on the VULCAN dataset performed best; therefore, we applied its optimal hyperparameters to predict emissions in other global cities. To ensure that target cities exhibit predictor distributions similar to those of the VULCAN training set, we conducted a Mahalanobis-distance-based filtering as follows[37]:

From the cleaned VULCAN training data, compute the mean vector μ and covariance matrix Σ (adding a small diagonal perturbation to ensure invertibility), then for each candidate urban area with predictor vector x , calculate the squared Mahalanobis distance

$$D^2(x) = (x - \mu)^\top \Sigma^{-1} (x - \mu).$$

Assuming multivariate normality, $D^2(x)$ follows a χ_d^2 distribution. We use the 90% quantile $\chi_{d,0.90}^2$ as a threshold, retaining only those cities with

$$D^2(x) \leq \chi_{d,0.90}^2,$$

and excluding all others. This procedure ensures that we apply the VULCAN-tuned model parameters only to cities within the 90% confidence region of the VULCAN feature space, thereby enhancing prediction reliability.

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